

Appendix

Interview Protocol

A Study for Exploring Information Literacy of PhD Research Student: Based on Thesis Topic Discovery Process

A. The Significance of This Study

In selecting a topic, most students focus on trying to be original and exhibiting the desire to contribute to the existing knowledge base. Most universities and doctoral faculties agree that a dissertation should be an original piece of research and should make a significant contribution to the field.

The way to begin developing a researchable topic is to look around you at the activities in which you are involved and to draw on your own personal and professional experiences. Most students find that they can best access areas in which they already have substantial expertise or familiarity with practice in the field or existing research. Once you have identified an area of interest, begin to examine and become familiar with the available literature related to your topic. Especially useful are reviews of literature found in journal, encyclopedias, yearbooks, and handbooks. You also might take time to look over earlier dissertation and seek previous studies that some respect for your topic.

This research will hopefully contribute to understanding the doctoral experience to obtain research topic through information literacy, and so the potential benefit of this study is improvement of higher education practice. Every effort will be made that all information provided by you will be treated as strictly confidential. All data will be coded and securely stored, and will be used for professional purposes only.

B. The Collection of Data

Appreciations to information from PhD Student:

- Interview PhD student to get detailed data of information literacy for the research topic discovery process.
- Interview through directly to PhD students in Taiwan and by skype for PhD student others country.

C. The Summary of Study

1. How PhD student obtains knowledge how to use information literacy.
2. How PhD student obtains information about a research topic.
3. How important information literacy for PhD student.

D. The Interview Content

Title of interview content	Interview content	Interview assumed time	Interview subject
Information Literacy Education for PhD student	What do you know information literacy education? Describe the sources and type information literacy is acquired?	5 mins	PhD Students
Information Obtaining Route for PhD student	How do you obtain information literacy? What resources do you use and what type information sought? What considerations are often used to determine information literacy as a reference for the research topic?	10 mins	PhD Students
Information Literacy for PhD student	How activities of information literacy, from the information need, information acquisition, evaluation of information, utilization of information, information ethics, self-motivated learning, and others?	10 mins	PhD Students
Obstacles of information literacy for PhD student	What obstacles of information literacy for PhD student during the search process research topic?	5 mins	PhD Students

E. Demographic Data

1. My gender is: Female Male
2. My age is: 23-30 31-40 41-50 50+
3. Occupation: _____
4. University (specify program and department):

5. Discipline/area of research: _____
6. Year in doctoral program to date: _____